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The Nexus Between Government Agricultural Expenditure And Food Security: A Case Of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The global food crisis of the 1970s, along with the 1974 World Food Conference, brought significant attention to food security and the role of government in improving food production, stabilizing food supplies, and managing food surpluses. In Nigeria, the agricultural sector, which remains the backbone of the economy, faces persistent challenges, particularly poor funding and the effects of climate change, both of which have severe implications for food security. This study examines the relationship between government agricultural expenditure and food security in Nigeria. Using canonical least squares (CLS) technique, the study analyzes secondary data on key variables, including government agricultural expenditure, food price inflation, population growth, food security, and climate change. The study adopts an ex-post facto design and sources quantitative data from the World Development Indicators (WDI) databank, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletins, and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) for the period; Q1 1986 to Q4 2023. The findings reveal that government agricultural expenditure has a significant positive impact on food security, with a coefficient of 0.000144 and a probability value of 0.0000. However, climate change negatively affects food security, with a coefficient of -2.8086 and a probability value of 0.0098. Based on these findings, the study recommends the establishment of an agricultural trust fund, the effective implementation of large-scale irrigation and dry-season farming programs, the adoption of mechanized farming systems, compulsory youth agricultural programs, Climate-Smart Agriculture practices, adherence to early warning systems, and flood/yield-based insurance programs.

Keywords: Food Security, Government Agricultural Expenditure, Climate change, Food price inflation, Population Growth Rate, Nigeria.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The discussions during the first United Nations conference at the height of World War II in 1943 marked the beginning of the global quest for food security. Additionally, among the fundamental rights highlighted by President Roosevelt before the U.S. entered the war was the “freedom from want everywhere in the world” (Shaw, 2007). The first conference resolved that, in the light of global issues related to food and agriculture, it is possible to realize the aim of achieving food security that is both sufficient and appropriate for the well-being of all populations.

The problem of global food security also attracted the attention of United Nations, leading to inclusion of food security as one of her second Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). According to UN (2023), since 2015, there has been a startling rise in the worldwide problem of hunger and food insecurity.

In Africa, due to famine in the Sahel and Darfur, Sudan, the issue of food security came up in 1974, and originally referred to the production and accessibility of enough food (Gerlach, 2015). Nevertheless, the

reason for these and subsequent famine in Africa was not necessarily lack of food in the continent, or inadequate food production. Instead, they resulted from governments' inability or refusal to supply grain on time, as well as their failure to monitor and coordinate local food production, storage, and distribution networks (Lappé, Collins & Rosset, 1998; De Waal, 2018).

One major challenge to attainment of food security in Nigeria could be traced to poor government expenditure to agricultural sector. For instance, the total annual government expenditure from 2001 to 2005 was 824 billion naira. The expenditure for the agricultural sector made up a very tiny portion of the total, averaging about 14.7-billion-naira year on year, or less than 1.8 percent of the entire budget. Contrarily, over the same time frame, the budgets for the water, health, and education sectors each accounted for 5.1%, 7.8%, and 5.7% of the total budget respectively (NBS, 2006). In fact, the allocation of government expenditure to agricultural sector in Nigeria has fallen below the benchmark of 10% as recommended by Maputo declaration.

Figure 1.1: Trend Analysis of Budgetary Allocation to Agricultural Sector in Nigeria.

Source: Federal Budget Office

Figure 1.1 showed that agricultural sector in Nigeria has received paltry allocation between 2015 and 2023. The worst share allocation was 0.9% in 2015 with a steady rise to 3.61% share in 2019, which was the highest over the period of analysis. Unfortunately, the share of agricultural sector expenditure drastically dropped to 1.51% in 2020 with another marginal increase to 1.92% in 2021. The negligence of the agricultural sector once again reflected in the current fall of allocation to 1.25% in 2022, and continued fall in 2023 recording 1.11%. It is regrettable that government budgetary allocation to agricultural sector has not been responsive to food insecurity, and other economic challenges that are related to agriculture in Nigeria.

Another critical problem of food security across the globe is climate change. The existence of climate change and the regularity of its adverse effects pose serious risks to human life in many parts of the globe. Due to the unfavorable impacts of climate change, there is a need for international concern, mitigation initiatives, and support for policies that would limit human activity that contributes to climate change. Climate change which pertains to alterations in the average variability characteristics of the climate that endure for a considerable amount of time, usually several decades or more has constitute a major global concern. Unpredictable rainfall patterns make agricultural productivity uncertain, which limits the amount of food that is affordable, accessible, and available in Africa. Even with these obstacles, a small number

of African nations are leading the way in creating novel solutions, like implementing climate-smart farming methods to mitigate climate-related issues (IPCC, 2014).

Furthermore, Nigeria's population is expanding far more quickly than its resources, though, majority of the population in the rural areas have a source of labour to agricultural. Otekunrin, Otekunrin, Momoh, and Ayinde (2019) noted that; Nigeria's food insecurity is made worse by the country's rapid population increase. By 2050; it was projected that the country's population will hit 400 million. Therefore, if Nigeria hopes to increase food security in line with her increasing agricultural output, the need to micro-manage her population growth is *sine qua non*.

The argument that food security in Nigeria seems to be seriously threatened by the agricultural sector's inadequate funding by the government remains an issue of national concern. The agricultural stakeholders are worried that Nigeria has continued to be a significant net food importer despite having over 70 million hectares of arable land, according to statistics from the FAO. To show more on the fact that paltry funds have been invested in the agricultural sector of the country; a recent National Bureau of Statistics' examination of the budgetary allocation revealed that the amount allotted to the agricultural sector has revolved around 2 percent of the overall national budget. For instance, in 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, and 2024, the agricultural sector received 1.70%, 2%, 1.56%, 1.34%, 1.37%, 1.8%, 1.11%, and 1.32%, of national budget respectively.

The re-occurring argument has been; has Nigerian government allocated sufficient fund to agricultural sector for attainment of food security or not? This kind of controversy and probing question has called for more studies in identifying the linkage effect among government expenditure on agricultural sector and food security in Nigeria which necessitate this study. This study therefore covers the period from the first quarter of 1986 to the fourth quarter of 2023.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual literature

2.1.1 Concept of Government Agricultural Expenditure

The total expenditures incurred by the public authorities (federal, state, and local governments) for the purpose of advancing the economic and social well-being of the populace or meeting their collective needs is referred to as "public/government expenditure". Nearly every nation on earth has seen an increase in public and government spending. This is as a result of the State, and other public bodies' on-going, multifaceted activity expansion (Ezeanyej, 2017). The Government distributes public funds to various sectors of her economy including agriculture, national defence, health, education, and others; to promote production of commodities, redistribute income, and enhance the overall state of its economy.

On its own, government agricultural expenditure is the allocated public funds through budgeting, to agricultural sector, with the goal of increasing output and productivity of the sector, thereby stimulating economic growth as well as ensuring the attainment of food security. In the agricultural sector, government expenditure includes funding of sectorial policies and programs, provision of inputs, building of flood control facilities, drainage and irrigation systems, running or supporting veterinary services for farmers, offering of grants and subsidies to farmers, providing pest control, crop inspection, and provision of extension services. Increased agricultural productivity, improved farmers' income, reduced poverty and food insecurity, as well as enhanced environmental sustainability could all be achieved through effective agricultural expenditure (FAO, 2016)

2.1.2 Concept of Food Security

When everyone, everywhere, has physical and financial access to enough safe, nutrient-dense food that satisfies their dietary needs and food choices for an active and healthy life, there is "food security" (World Food Summit, 1996). This concept identifies and explains the four primary components of food security according to FAO, and as shown in Fig. 2.1.

Figure 2.1: FAO Food Security Component

2.1.3 Overview of Agricultural Sector in Nigeria

Nigeria is extraordinarily fortunate to have lush soil over much of its land. Of Nigeria's 34 million hectares of arable land, 28.6 million are utilized for pastures and meadows, and 6.5 million are used for permanent crops. Agriculture produces over 24 percent of Nigeria's GDP. Based on this, the development of the country has been considered to be heavily dependent on agriculture. Nigeria is an extremely lucky country in terms of its agricultural potentials. Sorghum, cocoa, pineapple, and palm oil are just a few of the agricultural commodities that Nigeria leads the world in producing. Nigeria is the globe's 2nd-largest producer of sorghum, right after the US. Nigeria also ranked fifth for both cocoa bean and palm oil production. In agricultural sector, a lot of primary commodities are being exported to foreign nations. Palm oil is among the top 10 export categories, with fruits, nuts, and seeds coming in second and third categories (Oyaniran, 2020).

According to FMARD (2022), about 70.8 million Nigeria's hectares of arable land are primarily used to grow rice, millet, guinea corn, yam, beans, cassava, and maize. Their census further showed that, almost 50% of agrarian households in Nigeria grew maize, the most common crop in the country. Cassava crops come next, with 46% of families growing this root. Approximately 20% to 30% of the houses surveyed also grew beans, yams, and Guinea maize.

In real terms, Nigeria's agricultural sector grew by 3.16 percent (YoY) in the 1st quarter of 2022, a decrease of 0.42 percent from the 3.58 percent growth rate of the previous quarter. In real terms, agricultural sector's contribution to the GDP in 2022 Q1 was 22.3 percent, which was both greater than the first quarter of 2021 and lower than the fourth quarter of 2021, when it was 22.35 percent and 26.84 percent, respectively. In 2022 Q1, the agricultural sector saw nominal growth of 11.55% year over year, a decrease of 3.59 percent from the corresponding quarter in 2021.

2.2 Theoretical Literature

2.2.1 Wagner Theory of Public Expenditure

Adolph Wagner, a German economist developed this theory of increasing activities of the state due to the rising needs of the people. According to Wagner's law, when the industrial economy grows, there will be a matching increase in government expenditure that will be evidenced in gross domestic product of the country. Therefore, increased government expenditure is a function of improved rate of industrialization and economic growth. This further implies that real per capita income of countries rises during their

industrialization stage of development (Hana, 2018). As the growing needs of the society increase with the population growth, the need for increased government expenditure to improve welfare of the people through agriculture arises. Thus, more government spending is required to increase food production as well as ensure consistent supply of food for human consumption.

The expenditures of the government can be intensively or extensively increased based on the economic activities of the State. Thus, this theory stipulates that a functional relationship abound between the growth of the economy and the expenditures of the government to her various sectors such as agriculture, health, infrastructure etc. Wagner argued that government must intervene whenever there is failure in the market mechanism to reactivate growth in the economy through expansionary fiscal measures.

2.2.2 FAO Global Food Security Framework

In response to the growing issue of hunger and the disjointed governance surrounding food security, the Committee on World Food Security (CFS) Member States decided to undertake a comprehensive reform in 2008. The CFS Reform, which was approved by all CFS Member countries in 2009, restructures the organization's mission and objective to become “the first open global and governmental framework for a wide spectrum of dedicated stakeholders to operate jointly in a cohesive way and in cooperation with national-led procedures regarding the eradication of hunger and ensuring food security for all people (FAO, 2009).

The goal of the GFSF, which is a dynamic framework that has been adopted by CFS, is to enhance coordinating and direct collaborative action by several food security actors. Because of its flexibility, the GFSF can be modified when influencing variables shift. The primary additional benefit of the GFSF is that it offers a comprehensive framework with useful advice on fundamental suggestions for food security plans, policies, and initiatives that are supported by the extensive ownership, involvement, and input that CFS is able to provide (CFS, 2022).

2.3 Empirical Literature

The causal relationship between total expenditures and food supply in Saudi Arabia was investigated by Alkunain, Elzaki, and Al-Mahish in 2024. For the observation period of 2000–2020, the study used multivariate modeling techniques of the Granger Causality Test, Forecast Error Variance Decomposition (FEVD), Impulse Response Function (IRF), and Vector Auto regression (VAR). The study discovered that the supply of food in Saudi Arabia is significantly impacted by government spending.

Using the ARDL technique, De and Dahun (2018) investigated the short and long-term link between Meghalaya's agricultural output and government spending on agriculture and related sectors. The Bounds test result indicated that the variables in the study have a long-term cointegrating connection. The findings also showed that whereas public spending on education and transportation has a significantly favorable impact on agricultural output, public spending on agriculture and related activities has a significantly negative long-term impact.

In their 2023 study, Sylvia and Bowo examined how the agricultural sector affected food security using panel data, which combined cross-sectional data from 22 East Nusa Tenggara province districts and cities of Indonesia with time series data from 2018–2021. The study's conclusions demonstrated that, in Indonesia, local government spending has a non-significantly positive impact on food security, whereas the province's agriculture sector has a considerable negative impact.

Applying the VAR technique, Shri, Nor'Aznin, and Amir (2014) examined the dynamic link between a few macroeconomic variables and food security in Malaysia. The study discovered that food security in Malaysia is positively impacted by both government spending and population increase.

Employing the ordinary least squares method, Zaharia, Shonkwiler, Mocan and Tudorache

(2024) examined the effects of imports, government spending, employment, and climate change on the value of Romanian agricultural output. According to the study's findings, climate change has a detrimental effect on Romania's agricultural output and, consequently, on its sustainable development.

Soko (2022) assessed how governmental agricultural spending affected food production in Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. Using a fixed effects modeling technique, the study used country-level panel data for 25

countries in Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. The study found that food production in Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa is positively correlated with public agricultural spending.

Abdulrahman (2013) studied the impact of agricultural sector expenditure on food security in Nigeria covering the period of 1985 to 2010, and made use of simple linear regression analysis. The study adopted total agricultural output as dependent variable, and government expenditure on agricultural sector as the only explanatory variable. Results of the analysis indicated that food security in Nigeria has been significantly influenced by the budgetary allocation.

Akintunde, Adesope, and Okoruwa (2013) took a critical analysis of the effect of government expenditure and monetary policy on the Nigeria's agricultural output from 1980 to 2012, using ordinary least squares method. Taking agricultural sector output of the current year as its dependent variable; the study adopted one year lag of interest rate, one year lag of foreign private investment, one year lag of government annual budgetary allocation, one year lag of exchange rate, one year lag of consumer price index, one year lag of interest rate, and one year lag of agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund as its independent variables. The outcome of the study indicated that government expenditure on agriculture has a negative effect on the agricultural output of Nigeria for the period under consideration.

In assessing the effect of government expenditure on agricultural sector on output of agriculture in Nigeria within the scope of 1980 to 2013, Aina and Omojola (2017) adopted ordinary least squares method and error correction mechanism. The study specified her model with agricultural output, government recurrent expenditure on agriculture, and government capital expenditure on agriculture as its dependent and explanatory variables respectively. The study found a positive significant effect of agricultural expenditure on agricultural productivity in Nigeria within the ambit of the study.

Kanu (2017) also assessed the effect of government expenditure on agricultural production in Nigeria, using error correction mechanism and granger causality test. The following variables; volume of bank loan to agriculture, private sector contribution, quantity of food production, and management of fund were included in the model of the study. A unidirectional causal relationship; from government expenditure, and management of fund, to quantity of food production in Nigeria was found by the study. Again, agricultural expenditure was found to have negatively influenced quantity of food production in Nigeria over the period of analysis.

Idoko and Jatto (2018) in their own part studied the impact of government expenditure on agriculture on the economic growth of Nigeria, employing ordinary least squares method with observations from 1985 to 2015. The study included capital formation, domestic savings, government expenditure on agriculture, commercial bank credit to agriculture, and real gross domestic product as variables of its model. The results of the study showed that government expenditure on agriculture significantly influenced economic growth in Nigeria.

Empirically evaluating the nexus between public expenditure in agriculture and the output growth in Nigeria, Olawumi and Adesanmi (2018) employed secondary data ranging from 1982 to 2016 in their research. Proxying gross domestic product as a measure for economic growth, and including agricultural sector output and total government expenditure as explanatory variables; the study estimated her model using ordinary least squares method. The outcome of the study indicated that Nigeria's economic growth has been positively influenced by the government expenditure in agriculture over the period of the study.

Okonkwo, Nwosu, Okoroigwe, and Kalu (2019) assessed the impact of agricultural expenditure on the growth of agriculture sector in Nigeria from 1981 to 2017, using Engle-Granger two step techniques to estimate its model. The variables of their study were gross domestic per capita, agriculture implicit price deflator rate, population growth rate, total government expenditure on agriculture and economic services, average precipitation rainfall, and agricultural sector loans. The analysis of the study showed that agricultural growth in Nigeria has been negatively influenced by the total government expenditure in the short run.

Falana (2021) studied impact of agricultural expenditure on Nigeria's agricultural output using granger causality test as its methodology. The study covered the period of 1961 to 2013, and adopted agricultural growth rate, agricultural capital expenditure, agricultural output, and agricultural recurrent expenditure as

its variables. The findings of the study indicated a bi-directional causality between agricultural expenditure and agricultural output in Nigeria for the period under consideration.

The role of budgetary allocation and interventions of the central bank in attainment of food security in Nigeria was examined by Sakiru (2021) using ex-post facto research method. The study spanned from 2000 to 2018 employing food security, total budgetary allocation to agricultural sector, and total Central Bank of Nigeria interventions to agriculture sector as its variables. The findings of the study indicated that budgetary allocation to agricultural sector has no substantial effect on the attainment of food security in Nigeria.

The contribution of agriculture to providing food security in emerging nations, including Nigeria, was evaluated by Pawlak and Kołodziejczak (2020) using cluster analysis approach. The study observed that while agricultural sector actively works to increase food availability in both rich and developing nations of the world, food security has grown to be a problem of paramount concern for nations with varying levels of economic development. The findings of the study also showed that oil producing countries with diverse economic development levels, such as Iraq, Angola, Nigeria, or Ecuador, who are located on separate continents, were impacted by the physical and/or economic unavailability of food.

In their examination of the impact of various sources of agricultural financing on food security in Nigeria, Bernard and Bilyaminu (2022) adopted autoregressive distributed lag approach to analyze secondary data, spanning from 1981 to 2020. Their variables included government expenditure on agriculture, agricultural output, interest rate, agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund, inflation rate, and commercial credits. The study showed that agricultural expenditure and other sources of agricultural financing have significantly influenced food security in Nigeria.

In their study on government spending and agricultural output in Nigeria, Akpan and Akpanabah (2022) also adopted auto distributed lag approach, and employed time series data ranging from 1980-2018. The study included banks' credit to agricultural sector, agricultural output, government recurrent expenditure on agriculture, agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund, and government capital expenditure on agriculture as variables of its model. The analysis of the study showed that government expenditure has significantly influenced output of agricultural sector under the timeline of this study.

In their study on agricultural spending and agricultural output in Nigeria, Kuzhe, Eze, and Oniore (2023) covered the period of 1986 to 2021. Employing autoregressive distributed lag approach; the study included government total spending on agriculture, government recurrent spending on agriculture, agricultural sector productivity, and government capital spending on agriculture as variables of its model. The finding of the study indicated the presence of a strong positive impact from the government spending on agricultural output in Nigeria.

Sadiq (2023) explored the effect of government expenditure on agricultural productivity in Nigeria from 1985-2018 with the use of ordinary least squares technique for data analysis. The variables adopted in the study were, government agricultural expenditure, agricultural output and agricultural credit. Government expenditure was found to have negatively impacted on agricultural productivity in Nigeria for the period of this study.

Itodo, Apeh, and Adeshina (2012) used the Cob-Douglas production function and the ordinary least squares (OLS) technique to estimate a multiple regression of agricultural output against a number of variables as they looked at the effects of government spending on agriculture and agricultural output in Nigeria. The findings of the study showed that an insignificant positive relationship exists between government spending on agriculture and agricultural output.

More recently, the effect of agricultural expenditures on agricultural productivity and food security in Nigeria was examined by Dada, Posu, Omoare, Abalaba, and Oguntebe (2023). The study adopted finite distributed lag model approach, and covered the period of 1990 to 2019. The variables employed in the model were food security, agricultural productivity, and agricultural expenditure. The findings of the study showed that past expenditures on agricultural sector have significant impact on agricultural productivity and food security in Nigeria.

3.1 METHODOLOGY

This study is quantitative in nature, due to its adoption of secondary data, and ex-post facto methodology. The theoretical framework of this study is anchored on the Food and Agricultural Organization’s (FAO’s) global food security framework, 2009.

Therefore, the FAO’s 2009 food security framework is restated thus:

$$\text{Food Security} = f(\text{Governance, Economic issues, Demographic matters, Climatic factors}), \dots, (3.1)$$

Drawing from (3.1), the functional model of the study is expressed thus:

$$\text{Food Security} = f(\text{Government Agricultural Expenditure, Food Price Inflation, Population Growth rate, Climate Change, } Z_t) \dots (3.2)$$

Where; Government Agricultural Expenditure represents Governance, Food Price Inflation represents Economic issues, Population Growth rate represents Demographic matters, and Climate change represents Climatic factors as expressed in (3.1); while Z_t represents other variables that influenced food security but were not captured in (3.2).

3.2 Specification of Model

To achieve the objective of this study, the researcher adopts and modifies the model of Abdulrahaman (2013), which identifies the relevant independent variables for food security, and based on its proven success in similar research:

The model of Abdulrahaman (2013):

$$FS = \omega_0 + \omega_1 \text{gea} + \beta$$

Where;

FS = Food security (Total Agricultural Output)

ω_0 = Intercept

ω_1 = Coefficient of the independent variable

gea = Government expenditure on agricultural sector

β = Error term.

Therefore:

$$FS = f(\text{GAEXP, FPINFR, POPGR, CLC, AGINF}) \dots (3.3)$$

Where;

FS = Food Security using Global Food Security Index as a proxy

GAEXP = Government Agricultural Expenditure

FPINFR = Food Price Inflation Rate

POPGR = Population Growth Rate

CLC = Climate Change

AGINF = Agricultural Infrastructure

(i) The Government Agricultural Expenditure (GAEXP) affects food security through altering agricultural productivity. (ii) Food Price Inflation rate (FPINFR) is involved to replicate inflationary forces on the level of food prices which influences access to food (iii) Population Growth Rate (POPGR) is included to show that changes in population of Nigeria determine the number of available labour for agricultural production which affects agricultural output. (iv) Climate Change (CLC) is incorporated because of its effects on agricultural productivity through variations in precipitation. (v) Agricultural Infrastructure (AGINF) is adopted due to its capacity to enhance agricultural production as well as availability of food.

3.2.1 Econometric Equations

For estimating the formulated model of this study, the researcher transforms the functional models into econometric equations below:

For model one in (3.3); $FS = f(\text{GAEXP, FPINFR, POPGR, CLC, AGINF})$:

$$FS_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{LOGGAEXP}_t + \alpha_2 \text{FPINFR}_t + \alpha_3 \text{POPGR}_t + \alpha_4 \text{CLCS}_t + \alpha_5 \text{LOGAGINF}_t$$

$$+ \mu_t \dots (3.4)$$

Where;

α_0 is the intercept,

$\alpha_1 - \alpha_5$ represents coefficients of the explanatory variables,

μ^t = error term.

3.3 Source of Data

The description and sources of data used in this study is stated in table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Description of Data

Series	Description	Unit of Measurement	Apriori Expectation	Source
FS	Food Security proxied with Global Food Security Index.	Index number		World Development Indicators (WDI) of World Bank
CLC	Climate change represented with precipitation variation.	Millimeters (mm)	Negative	World Development Indicators (WDI) of World Bank
AGINF	Agricultural Infrastructure.	Units	Positive	World Development Indicators (WDI) of World Bank
FPINFR	Food Price Inflation Rate.	Percentage (%)	Negative	Statistical Bulletins of Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) for various years.
GAEXP	Government Agricultural Expenditure.	Naira (N)	Positive	Budget Office of the Federation
POPGR	Population growth rate	Percentage (%)	Positive	National Bureau of Statistics (NBS)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Stationary Test

To identify the effect of government agricultural expenditure on food security in Nigeria, the researcher first conducts a stationarity test on all the variables used in the study. This preliminary test is crucial to avoid the risk of generating spurious regression results. Accordingly, Table 4.1 presents the KPSS stationarity test results.

Table 4.1: Results for Kwiatkoski Phillip Shmidit and Shin (KPSS) Stationary Test

Series	KPSS Level Form	Critical Test Value @ 5%	Integration Order	Interpretation
POPGR	0.232352*	0.463	I(0)	Stationary at Level
D(CLC)	0.035902**	0.463	I(1)	Stationary at 1st Difference
D(FS)	0.09245**	0.463	I(1)	Stationary at 1st Difference
D(FPINFR)	0.057094**	0.463	I(1)	Stationary at 1st Difference
D(LOGGAEXP)	0.038753**	0.463	I(1)	Stationary at 1st Difference
D(AGINF,2)	0.127876***	0.463	I(2)	Stationary at 2nd Difference

Source: E-views Output.

Note: * denotes stationary at level.

** denotes stationary at first difference.

*** denotes stationary at second difference.

For the KPSS computation, the lag truncations for the Bartlett kernel were selected according to Newey and West (1987). The results of the stationary test indicate that the Population Growth Rate (POPGR) variable is integrated of order zero, denoted as I(0). Also, the Climate Change (CLC), Food Security (FS), Food Price Inflation Rate (FPINFR), and Government Agricultural Expenditure (GAEXP) variables are integrated of order one, denoted as I(1). Meanwhile, Agricultural Infrastructure (AGINF) is integrated of order two, denoted as I(2). This implies that the POPGR series is stationary at their level forms, while the CLC, FS, FPINFR, and GAEXP series are stationary at their first differences, and AGINF series is stationary at its second differences. Therefore, to achieve spurious-free regression results, the study adopts all variables at their stationary levels.

4.2 Test of Hypothesis

To achieve the objective of this study, the researcher tests the null hypothesis that Government agricultural expenditure has no significant effect on food security in Nigeria.

Table 4.8: Government Agricultural Expenditure and Food Security in Nigeria.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOGGAEXP	0.000144	2.26E-05	6.379945	0.0000
FPINFR	0.01063	0.021118	0.503375	0.6155
POPGR	-67.33685	3.436265	-19.59594	0.0000
CLC	-4.09533	1.226842	-3.338108	0.0011
LOGAGINF	0.004567	0.000101	45.08224	0.0000
C	151.66+78	9.289239	16.32726	0.0000

Source: E-views Output.

According to the results in Table 4.8, the study found that government agricultural expenditure in Nigeria is positively related to food security, with a coefficient value of 0.000144 for the government agricultural expenditure variable. Since the probability value for the LOGGAEXP series (0.0000) is less than 5%, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis that government agricultural expenditure has a significant effect on food security in Nigeria. Similarly, food price inflation (FPINFR) and agricultural infrastructure (LOGAGINF) also show a positive relationship with food security. In contrast, population growth (POPGR) was found to have a negative relationship with food security in Nigeria.

4.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

This study finds that government agricultural expenditure has a significant positive effect on food security in Nigeria, supporting the study's apriori expectations. Additionally, this result aligns with the findings of Bernard and Bilyaminu (2022), Aina and Omojola (2017), and Abdulrahaman (2013). The study's outcome also highlights the importance of increased government spending in Nigeria's agricultural sector in achieving food security. However, the effect of government agricultural expenditure on food security is relatively modest, with a coefficient of 0.000144. This implies that a unit increase in government agricultural expenditure leads to only a 0.0001-unit increase in food security. Therefore, the study suggests that both public and private sectors should increase agricultural funding to enhance food security in Nigeria. To attract private investors to the agricultural sector, the government must create favorable investment conditions, such as developing agro-infrastructure facilities.

This study also found that the population growth rate has a negative effect on food security in Nigeria. This result aligns with the study's apriori expectation and supports the finding of Tavershima, Kotur andTseaa (2022). While Nigeria's large population could be effectively utilized in agriculture, the majority of the population, particularly the youth, show less interest in farming due to the low level of mechanization in agricultural production. Therefore, it is crucial for the government to transform the agricultural system, making it more attractive to the younger population and harnessing their potentials in

agribusiness. Increased mechanization and reduced reliance on outdated farming methods will lead to higher agricultural productivity and improved food security in the country.

Finally, the findings of this study also show that climate change has an unfavorable impact on food security in Nigeria. This result, which aligns with the study's apriori expectation, corroborates the finding of Adesete, Olanubi, and Dauda (2022). The study also reveals that food security declines by roughly 3 units for every unit increase in climate change. By decreasing agricultural productivity, the destructive effects of floods, droughts, and other climate shocks lead to a significant decline in food security. Over the past few decades, annual precipitation fluctuations and trends in Nigeria have exhibited inter-annual variations that have triggered extreme weather events such as droughts and floods in various regions. These events have caused the loss of livestock and crop yields, thereby jeopardizing Nigeria's food security. Climate change also negatively impacts natural resources, reducing their capacity to provide essential agricultural products, which are critical for human consumption and serve as the primary source of livelihood and income for most Nigerian farmers. There is also a growing public concern that Nigeria's already high level of food insecurity is being worsened by climate change, which is causing displacement in several States. Agrarian communities living in areas where unchecked resource depletion has led to climate-induced land degradation are particularly vulnerable to the instability caused by climate change. Therefore, the Nigerian government must urgently implement policies and activities to reduce the vulnerability of Nigerians in the agricultural sector to climate change, while also improving adaptation and mitigation measures. These efforts are crucial for increasing the nation's food production, sufficiency, sustainability, and overall food security.

5.1 Recommendations

In light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Establishment of an Agricultural Trust Fund (ATF): This fund will serve as a dedicated reserve for the implementation of agricultural projects and programs. The government should allocate a certain percentage of its revenue to the ATF to enhance agricultural expenditure, boost productivity, and improve food security in Nigeria. Additionally, non-State actors and diaspora investors should be encouraged to contribute to the ATF, diversifying its funding sources. The establishment of the ATF is also expected to broaden agricultural financing and support the development of agro-infrastructure for sustainable agricultural production in Nigeria.
- ii. The government should encourage the effective implementation of massive irrigation systems and dry season farming policies. Irrigation enables year-round farming and enhances farmers' resilience to climate change impacts, such as flooding and irregular rainfall pattern. Therefore, to control food price inflation and mitigate the effects of climate change, the government should invest in establishing irrigation facilities and promoting dry season farming, as opposed to the current reliance on rain-fed agriculture, which has become unreliable due to irregular precipitation patterns caused by climate change.
- iii. The government should increase the level of mechanized farming in Nigeria. Although this study found a positive relationship between population growth and agricultural output, the current crude farming methods are unsustainable and unlikely to achieve the nation's food security goals. Moreover, the youth, who make up a large portion of the population, are increasingly disinterested in such labour-intensive methods, depriving the country of the able-bodied workforce needed for optimal agricultural productivity. Therefore, to reduce the over-reliance on human labour and support the achievement of food security, improving mechanized farming in Nigeria is crucial.
- iv. The government should establish compulsory youth agricultural programs for graduates and school leavers in Nigeria. These programs aim to spark the interest of young people in farming enterprises, engaging them early in agribusiness. Since youth make up the majority of the population, attracting them to agriculture can reduce unemployment, boost agricultural productivity, and enhance food security in Nigeria. .

- v. Farmers should embrace climate-smart agricultural practices, including the use of drought-resistant crop varieties, improved crop strains, early-maturing crops, and other adaptive management techniques. These practices enhance resilience to climate change while increasing agricultural productivity.
- vi. Early Warning Systems: The government should effectively utilize meteorological data and early warning systems to provide timely information on weather patterns, pest outbreaks, and other climate-related risks. This will help Nigerian farmers make informed decisions regarding planting, irrigation, and harvesting. Additionally, farmers should be encouraged to strictly follow the early warning systems and weather forecasts provided by the Nigerian Meteorological Agency.
- vii. Finally, farmers should adopt flood and yield-based insurance programs. They should be encouraged and supported by the government to enrol in agricultural insurance schemes to mitigate the unavoidable impacts of climate change, particularly in flood- and drought-prone areas. This will help reduce losses due to flooding, control food price inflation, and enhance food security in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Nigeria's food security challenges are multifaceted, involving insufficient government expenditure, climate change, and rapid population growth. Addressing these requires strategic investments, climate adaptation measures, and robust policy reforms. This study provides a roadmap for achieving sustainable food security, aligning with global and regional development goals.

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